

Equal-Life Harmonisation Manual
Outcomes, exposures and mediator variables

Version 2

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Aim

The aim of this document is to provide a manual for the harmonisation of outcome-, exposure- and mediator-data across the cohorts of the Equal-Life project, aligning with the WP7 task 7.1 (see more details in the grant agreement). The harmonisation strategy is based on an adaptation of the harmonisation manual developed in the LifeCycle project (1) as well as the Molgenis database (2) to the extent possible. As a result of this harmonisation process, variables generated within each cohort participating in Equal-Life will be comparable.

Variable selection and prioritisation process

Selection and Prioritisation

The selection and prioritisation process leading up the harmonised indicators and final variables described in this document, started at the conception of the project. Since the start, definition documents were produced to describe the relevant mental health and cognitive outcomes (see definition documents for further details); and lists of exposome variables were created, rated and shortened to only contain the most relevant ones (for a more detailed description, see e.g., deliverable 5.5). In parallel, WP7 carried out a variable grouping exercise that described the content of the participating cohort and school studies, and thereafter mapped the availability of outcomes, exposures and mediators and across cohorts. Further, outcome-based teams (mental health diagnosis, internalizing symptoms/externalizing behaviour, well-being, and cognitive development) further worked on specifying research questions and selecting exposures and outcomes. All this prior work constitutes the foundation of the cohort-variables included in the harmonisation and codebooks described within this document. Version 2 of the harmonisation protocol is still in progress, and as the work proceeds in the project and within the teams this harmonisation protocol will be updated and newer versions will be published.

Data availability

The indicators that are available for harmonisation in term of outcomes, the social exposome, the physical exposome and enrichment, are outlined in the tables below. The specific items corresponding to these items can be found in the codebooks also included in this document.

Outcomes

Table 1 provides a concept list of the available outcomes, i.e., mental health, wellbeing, and cognitive development outcomes.

Table 1. List of mental health, wellbeing, and cognitive development outcomes available in cohort and school studies in Equal-Life		
Mental Health	Wellbeing	Cognitive development
Externalizing behaviour	General Health	Selective attention
Internalizing symptoms	Medically unexplained symptoms	Inhibition
Psychological distress/total difficulties	Life satisfaction	Working memory
ADHD	Happiness	Reasoning
Autism	Pro-social behaviour	Reading ability
Anxiety		Dyslexia
Depression		School achievement/grades

Social and physical exposome indicators

Table 2 provides a concept list of the available data on the social exposome indicators available in the cohort.

Table 2. List of social exposome indicators indicated concepts to be harmonised
Sociodemographic variables
Age (child, mother, father)
Sex
Migration background (child, mother, father)
Language
Socioeconomic variables
Education (child, mother, father)
Employment (child, mother, father)
Socioeconomic situation
Material living conditions
Actors
Regular contacts
Family structure and Members of household
Companions
Peers
Relational dynamics: Social support
Social support by non-family members
Parental/familial investment
Relational dynamics: Social climate/atmosphere
Harmony/Disharmony
Quality of relationship
Parental style/practices
Adaptive/maladaptive Living conditions
Places
Places for learning/care
Type of Home
Leisure time
Neighbourhood social environment
Digital world
Norms & Values
Cultural values
Social norms

Table 3 provides a concept list of the available data on the physical exposome indicators available in the cohorts.

Table 3. List of physical exposome indicators/indicated concepts to be harmonised
Air quality outdoor Residential /school/preschool
Air pollution – PM (residential, school)
Air pollution – NO2 (residential, school)
Air pollution – NOX (residential)
Air pollution – black carbon (school)
Sound/Noise quality outdoor Residential/school/preschool Outdoor
Noise pollution (residential, school)
Passive smoking
Mother smoking during pregnancy
Child passive smoking
Indoor environmental quality at home /school/preschool (moulds/dust/dampness/overall)
Dampness – residential
Crowding Residential /Preschool and school
Crowding – residential
Crowding - school
Access to green space (residential. Preschool, school, “en route”)
Green space – residential
Green space – school
Access to blue space (residential. Preschool, school, en route)
Blue space – residential
Smoking
Child smoking
Age starting smoking
Smoking no. of cigarettes
Substance use
Alcohol
Drugs
Food: healthy food intake, breast feeding
Breast feeding
Fruit intake
Vegetable intake
Snack intake
Dietary supplemental intake
Intake of sweet drinks

Specific food groups
Food allergy/intolerance
Birth outcomes
Low birth weight
Small for gestational age
Preterm birth

Mediators

Table 4 provides a concept list of the available data on the mediators available in the cohorts.

Table 4. List of mediator concepts to be harmonised
Sleep
Sleep quality/insomnia
Sleep duration
Stress
Stressful/critical life events
Perceived stress
Noise annoyance
Noise interference
Self-regulation/coping (limited ability to harmonise due to incompatibility across cohorts)
Coping with noise at school
General coping styles
Self-regulation of emotional states
Self-regulation of behaviour

Enrichment data

As by publication of this version of the harmonisation protocol, physical enrichment exposome variables have been circulated to the cohorts by TUD and ISGlobal, which are available on Viadesk. Further, instructions for how to assess social enrichment exposome variables have been published in Milestone 16 (also available on Viadesk). An overview of delivered physical and social enrichment data can be found in **Table 4**, while the full variable-list of enrichment data can be found in the appendix of this document.

Table 4. List of physical and social enrichment data
Physical exposome
Street network variables
Greenspace accessibility variables

Sidewalk width variables
Building
Green and blue spaces
Land use
Population
Roads
Social exposome
Social interactions
Socioeconomic circumstances and Sociodemographic characteristics
Systems, institutions and priorities of the political economy
Sociodemographic characteristics with high impact on Social norms, Cultural values

Harmonisation

Harmonisation of variables is needed for the analyses that are to be conducted within each cohort. To facilitate harmonisation, a codebook has been developed for both the outcomes and exposures. The code book shows the harmonised variable name, the description of the variable, the values (operationalization), units, data type, further instructions/comments, and a column describing which cohorts have mapped this information (and hence should harmonise the variable). Further details on the table headings in the code book is shown in **Table 5**.

Variable name	Label/description	Values	Unit	Data Type	Further instructions	Mapped by
The name of the harmonised variable. This name needs to be match exactly with the derived (harmonised) variable	The description of the harmonised Equal-Life variable. There is no need to label variables	Details the categories for categorical and binary variables	Gives the units for continuous variables	The data type: continuous or categorical	Further specific instructions for harmonisation of this variable	Name of the cohorts that can create this variable

The codebook is included in this document as well as in a separate excel file (“Codebook_Equal-Life_version 1”) which also includes the specific items across cohorts, for each variable. This file is of particular importance to cohorts that have several assessments of the same concept at the same time point, as it is indicated in the file which of the assessments that should be harmonised.

Explanation of the variable names

As much as possible, the naming and operationalization of variables have been aligned with LifeCycle and molgenis catalogues. However, considering that Equal-Life is carrying out cohort-specific analysis on site, our variable names has been adapted to be more informative by adding additional details to the variable names (e.g., the reporter and the time/age of assessment). Since there has been no prioritization carried out based on the reporter of the information in Equal-Life, variables should be created for each reporter. This means that if information has been provided separately by e.g., parents and teachers, two separate variables will need to be created for each reporter. This is important for prioritization that might be conducted ahead, transparency when comparing results from analysis, as well as for possible sensitivity analyses. The general structure of the variable name is: **descriptive name_ui_r_t**. What each of these letters/abbreviations mean is described below in **Table 6**.

Abbreviation	Meaning	Possible values
ui	Unit of interest	ch (child), m (mother), f (father), p (parent/caretaker)
r	reporter of the information	cr (child), mr (mother), fr (father), pr (parent), tr (teacher), rr (register)
t	Assessment point (age)	The age of the child at assessment. A variable should be created for the year of assessment (e.g., 11). If repeated assessments were made separate variables need to be created for each year (e.g., for 11, 12, 13, 14, 15 and 16) and an additional variable for the range of years (e.g., 11_16). **Note** Creating multiple variables is more time-consuming but helps ensure we do not miss out on information that may be necessary for future research questions. Please see 'creating harmonised variables' section below.

Let's look at an example for the outcome variable: **ADHD_ch_r_t**, which you can also find included in the code book (below). In this example "ADHD" is the descriptive name, in this case representing ADHD diagnosis. "ch" is to state that the unit of interest is the "child". So, the variable will provide information on the ADHD diagnosis for the child. For ADHD, as in this example and as in other examples, data is harmonised across different rapporteurs, and the cohorts will hence need to fill in the "r" to indicate who reported the information. In other cases in which data is not harmonised across different rapporteurs, the "ui" will already be filled in in the codebook to indicate differences between e.g., child- and parent-reported data. Finally, the cohorts will need to fill in the age of the child when the data was measured (t). So, if the diagnosis was obtained from the teacher when the child was at age 11, the variable name will be "**ADHD_ch_tr_11**".

Preparation of the data

Harmonisation is done with data in the wide format. Start harmonising high-priority items, i.e., outcomes as well as variables that are coloured with green in the harmonisation tables below. These are the variables that will be applied in the first analyses.

Creating harmonised variables

As described in the section on the variable names, several variables will have to be created for some cohorts, if data was collected on the same outcome/exposure from several sources (reporter) and time-points (ages).

- Time-point/age: If an assessment was done once at age 7, then you only need to create the variables for that age. For repeated measures, please create variables for each age of assessment (as opposed to the average age of the cohort at follow-up), e.g., if we have the information of a child's father's educational level reported by the father when the child is at ages 11, 14, and 17, the cohort owners will need to create the following variables: Edu_f_fr_11; Edu_f_fr_14; Edu_f_fr_17.
- Rapporteur/source: if you have the same information reported by multiple sources, you will need to create a separate variable for each rapporteur. Using an example based on the exposure variable for educational level, if the educational level of the father has been reported by the mother as well as the father, you will need to create two variables one for the information reported by the mother "mr": a variable called "Edu_f_mr_11" and a variable for the information reported by the father "f": a variable called "Edu_f_fr_11". When data is not harmonized across different rapporteurs, the rapporteur will already be included in the variable name in the codebook.

Further, it is important for the analysis that the direction of response categories is the same across cohorts, so make sure that 0/lowest number denotes the lowest level of exposure/no outcome, while the highest number denotes the highest exposure/presence of outcome.

Handling missing values/data

If no data exist within your cohort for a given variable at any age or at specific ages, then skip these and do not create the variable. For example, if there are no records for ADHD diagnosis, then do not create any ADHD diagnosis variables.

The cohorts do not have to handle missing data within variables in the data preparation, as this will be handled by WP6 in the analysis-stage. It is important though that missings should be coded as blanks (missings) – do not indicate missings with any letters or numbers. If a variable has >25% missing values, then remove the variable altogether (note! this applies for when the cohort is complete, i.e., after drop-outs and other ineligible has been removed from the data).

If the missing actually indicates "No", i.e., indicates that an outcome or exposure is not present, then code it as 0 (for example in items asking if the child has a diagnosis = yes, else should be = 0).

Analysis and sharing of results

On the basis of the analysis protocols being prepared by the teams (which should contain the research question(s) the team would like to study, the type of analysis that will be applied, and the specific exposure-variables, mediators and outcomes of interest), WP6 will provide R-codes for the statistical analysis. Once the analysis has been completed by the cohort, the results should be uploaded to Viadesk.

Harmonisation tables

Below you can find harmonisation tables – codebooks – for outcomes, exposures and mediators. Please note that these are not yet finalized. For some of the variables you can hence find both the variable name as well as the suggested operationalisation across cohorts (i.e., how to categorise the actual variable), while in other cases only the variable name is available. Harmonisation is continuously ongoing, but the availability of the variable names provides an indication that this harmonised variable will be available in a later version of this document.

Harmonisation table for outcome variables

Table 5. Codebook for harmonisation of mental health, wellbeing, and cognitive outcome variables							
<i>Green-coloured rows = high-priority harmonisation-items</i>							
Mental Health							
Variable name	Label/description	Values	Unit	Data Type	Comments	Further instructions	Mapped by
ADHD_ch_r_t	Presence of ADHD-diagnosis or symptoms of child	0= no, 1=yes		Categorical	ADHD has been harmonized across different reports. If multiple items exist in a cohort, the following prioritization scheme has been applied: parental report, child report, teacher report. Further, prioritization has been given to items of diagnosis/reported diagnosis, and thereafter symptom scales.	For PIAMA: use bold item for age 14. For ALPINE: classify top 5% of scores as adhd (1=yes) (see excel-verison of code book for more information)	ABCD, ALPINE, BREATHE, NORAH, RANCH, PIAMA, WALNUTS, FAIR, ALSPAC

Autism_ch_r_t	Presence of autism diagnosis or symptoms of child	0= no, 1=yes		Categorical	Autism has been harmonized across different reports. If multiple items exist in a cohort, the following prioritization scheme has been applied: parental report, child report, teacher report. Further, prioritization has been given to items of diagnosis/reported diagnosis, and thereafter symptom scales.		ABCD, PIAMA, WALNUTS, FAIR, ALSPAC
Dep_ch_r_t	Presence of depression diagnosis or symptoms of the child	<i>Consult the team</i>					ABCD, PIAMA, FAIR, FINNTWIN, ALSPAC
Anx_ch_r_t	Presence of anxiety diagnosis or symptoms of the child	<i>Consult the team</i>					ABCD, FAIR, FINNTWIN, ALSPAC
Wellbeing							
Variable name	Variable name	Variable name	Variable name	Variable name	Variable name	Variable name	Variable name
<i>Not yet indicated</i>							
Cognitive development							
Variable name	Label/description	Values	Unit	Data Type	Comments	Further instructions	Mapped by
RRT_raw_Ch_cr_t	Raw scores from simple reaction time tests	Continuous	Raw scores (m/s)			If several tests were run in the same assessment,	<i>Consult the team</i>

						use the averaged raw score.	
RRT_std_Ch_cr_t	Standardized scores from simple reaction time tests	Continuous	Standardized raw scores (m/s)			If several tests were run in the same assessment, use the averaged raw score.	<i>Consult the team</i>

Harmonisation table for social exposome variables

Note: Selection of high-priority items for the social exposome is still pending.

Table 6. Codebook for harmonisation of social exposome variables							
Indicator/dimension	Variable name	Label/description	Values	Unit	Data Type	Further instructions	Mapped by
Meta-variables							
Child identifier	child_id	Unique identifier number for the index child				Either the original id or a new id generated by the cohort	
Sociodemographic variables							
Age/Date of birth	Dob_ch_report	Date of birth of the child	Yyyy/mm/dd	date			ABCD, FAIR, NORAH, RANCH
	Age_ch_r_t	Age (in years) at assessment, with report indicated.		year	continuous	If several measurement points exist, only use the first measurement point.	ABCD,ALPINE, BREATHE,FINNTWIN,NORAH, PIAMA,STARS,WALNUTS
	Dob_m_report	Date of birth of the mother	Yyyy/mm/dd	date			ABCD, FINNTWIN, PIAMA, RA
	Age_m_report_t	Age of mother (in years) at assessment		year	continuous		ALPINE, WALNUTS
	Agebirth_m_report	Age of mother (in years) in pregnancy/ at child birth		year	continuous		ABCD, ALPINE, FAIR
	Dob_f_report	Date of birth of the father	Yyyy/mm/dd	date			FINNTWIN, PIAMA, RANCH_M
	Age_f_report_t	Age of father (in years) at assessment		year	continuous		ABCD, WALNUTS?
Sex	Sex_ch_r	Biologically assigned sex of child	1=boy 2=girl		Categorical		ABCD, ALPINE, BREATHE, FAI FINNTWIN, NORAH, PIAMA, F ,STARS, WALNUTS
Migrant background	Cob_ch_r	Country of birth of child	0= born in country of study 1=born outside the country of study		Categorical		ABCD, BREATHE, NORAH, PIAMA,STARS, WALNUTS
	cob_f_r	Country of birth of father	0= born in country of		Categorical		ABCD, BREATHE, NORAH, PIAMA,RANCH,STARS, WALN

			study 1=born outside the country of study				
	Cob_m_r	Country of birth of mother	0= born in country of study 1=born outside the country of study		Categorical		ABCD, BREATHE, FAIR, FINNTWIN,NORAH, PIAMA,RANCH,STARS, WALN
Language	Language_ch_r_t	Language spoken at home	1=Official language of the study country 2=other		Categorical		ABCD, APLINE, BREATHE,NO RANCH
Socioeconomic variables							
Education	Edu_ch_r_t	School grade status for birth cohorts	<u>Low (primary school or less)</u> = <u>1Middle (secondary school or equivalent)</u> = <u>2High (University degree or higher)</u> = <u>3</u> <u>N/A = -99</u>		Categorical		ABCD, FINNTWIN, PIAMA BREATHE only has type of ed RANCH has number of years be made into primary/secondary/high base years of schooling)
	Edu_f_r_t	Father highest on-going or completed education	<u>High = 1</u> Short cycle tertiary, Bachelor, Masters, Doctoral or equivalent (ISCED-2011:		categorical	If more than one education level is reported within the defined time frame, use highest recorded education level. If you are unsure of the categories that apply in your	ABCD, BREATH, FINNTWIN, N PIAMA, RANCH, WALNUTS

			<p>5-8, ISCED-97: 5-6)</p> <p><u>Medium=2</u> Upper secondary, post-secondary non-tertiary (ISCED-2011: 3-4, ISCED-97: 3-4)</p> <p><u>Low=3</u> No education, early childhood, pre-primary, primary, lower secondary, or second stage of basic education (ISCED-2011: 0-2, ISCED-97: 0-2)</p>			<p>cohort, mapping tools for specific countries can be found here: http://uis.unesco.org/en/isced-mappings</p>	
	Edu_m_r_t	Mother highest on-going or completed education	<p><u>High = 1</u> Short cycle tertiary, Bachelor, Masters, Doctoral or equivalent (ISCED-2011:</p>		categorical	<p>If more than one education level is reported within the defined time frame, use highest recorded education level.</p> <p>If you are unsure of the categories that apply in your cohort, mapping tools for</p>	<p>ABCD, ALPINE, BREATH, FAIR, FINNTWIN, NORAH, PIAMA, WALNUTS</p>

			<p>5-8, ISCED-97: 5-6)</p> <p><u>Medium=2</u> Upper secondary, post-secondary non-tertiary (ISCED-2011: 3-4, ISCED-97: 3-4)</p> <p><u>Low=3</u> No education, early childhood, pre-primary, primary, lower secondary, or second stage of basic education (ISCED-2011: 0-2, ISCED-97: 0-2)</p>			<p>specific countries can be found here: http://uis.unesco.org/en/isced-mappings</p>	
Employment	occup_ch	Occupational status of the child	<p>1=paid job 2=no paid job</p>		categorical		FINNTWIN, PIAMA
	occuphour_ch_r_t	Working hours of the child	<p>1=more than 20hrs/week 2=less than 20hrs/week 3=other</p>		categorical		FINNTWIN, PIAMA
	occupcode_f_r_t	Occupational code of the father	<p>1=Legislators, senior officials, managers</p>		categorical		ABCD, FINNTWIN, NORAH, RA WALNUTS, FAIR

			2= Professionals 3= Technicians and associate professionals 4 = Clerks 5 = Service workers, and shop and market sale workers 6=Skilled agricultural, and fishery workers 7 =Craft and related trades workers 8=Plant and machine operators, and assemblers 9= Elementary occupations 0= Armed forces occupations			
	occup_f	Occupational status of the father	1=Employed 2=Self-employed 3=Unemployed 4=Student, apprentice, student 5=Domestic tasks (housewife		categorical	ABCD?, BREATHE, FINNTWIN NORAH, PIAMA?,RANCH, WA

			etc. 6= Inactive/other (Receiving benefits or pension etc.				
	occuphour_f	Working hours of the father	1=full time (>32 hrs per week) 2=part-time <= 32hrs per week) 3=not at all		categorical	Use the hour based cut-offs when applicable	ABCD, FAIR, FINNTWIN, RAN
	occupcode_m	Occupational code of the mother	1=Legislators, senior officials, managers 2= Professionals 3= Technicians and associate professionals 4 = Clerks 5 = Service workers, and shop and market sale workers 6=Skilled agricultural, and fishery workers 7 =Craft and related trades workers 8=Plant and machine		categorical		ABCD, ALPINE, FAIR, FINNTW NORAH, RANCH, WALNUTS

			operators, and assemblers 9= Elementary occupations 0= Armed forces occupations				
	occup_m	Occupational status of the mother	1=Employed 2=Self-employed 3=Unemployed 4=Student, apprentice, student 5=Domestic tasks (housewife etc. 6= Inactive/other (Receiving benefits or pension etc.		categorical	ABCD?, BREATHE, FAIR, FINN NORAH, PIAMA?, RANCH, WA	
	occuphour_m	Working hours of the mother	1=full time (>32 hrs per week) 2=part-time <= 32hrs per week) 3=not at all		categorical	Use the hour-based cut-offs when applicable	ABCD, FAIR, FINNTWIN, RAN
Socioeconomic situation	Hh_income_r_t	4th quartile (highest) = 1 3rd quartile = 2 2nd quartile = 3 1st quartile = 4	Total yearly income of the household. Categorised into quartiles of low,		categorical		FAIR, NORAH,RANCH_NL

			<p>medium-low, medium-high and high income levels based on national distribution of household yearly income</p> <p>If more than household income is recorded within the defined time frame, use highest recorded household income.</p> <p>Income will be categorised into quartiles (low, medium-low, medium-high, high) based on national distribution of household incomes in the year of follow-up.</p>				
Material living conditions	HH_computer	household owns computer	Yes=1 No=0		categorical	This is a variable that is not in Molgenis. This is a	FINNTWIN, PIAMA, STARS

						suggestion for harmonisation.	
	Child_room_r_t	Child has own room	Yes=1 No=0		categorical	This is a variable that is not in Molgenis. This is a suggestion for harmonisation.	ALPINE, FINNTWIN, PIAMA, S
	room_number_r_t	number of rooms			continious	Types of rooms are diffrent in different studies	ALPINE, NORAH, RANCH_NL,
Actors							
Regular contacts	childcare_r_t	Who conducted the childcare after school	Parents = 1 Grandparents =2 Babysitter =3 Another adult =4 other =5		Categorical		ABCD, FINTWINN, NORAH, PI
Family structure and Members of household	hh_adultsnr_r_t	number of adults in household			integer	From molgenis	ABCD, ALPINE, FAIR, FINTV NORAH, PIAMA, RANCH_M STARS, WALNUTS
	famsize_child	Total number of children under 18 years old in the household of study participant.			integer	From molgenis	ABCD, ALPINE, FAIR, FINTV NORAH, PIAMA, RANCH_M STARS, WALNUTS
Companions	Companions_ch_r_t	Does the child report having a good friend	Yes=1 No=0		Binary	This is a variable that is not in Molgenis. This is a suggestion for harmonisation.	ABCD, FINNTWIN, BREATH WALNUTS

Peers	Peers_ch_r_t	How often have do you play with your friends	1= Never 2= Rarely 3= Sometimes 4= Often 5= Always		categorical	This is a variable that is not in Molgenis. This is a suggestion for harmonisation.	ABCD, NORAH, STARS
Relational dynamics: Social support							
Social support by non-family members	Socialsupport_ch_r_t	Social support from friends	1= Never 2= Rarely 3= Sometimes 4= Often 5= Always			<p>This is a variable that is not in Molgenis. This is a suggestion for harmonisation.</p> <p>FINNTWIN has responses based on number of people available for support - unsure if this can be harmonised with the other cohorts.</p> <p>7-point likert scale in ABCD - potential to collapse some responses into 5 categories</p>	ABCD, PIAMA, STARS
Parental/familial investment	EmotionalSupport_ch_r_t	Emotional support from parents	1= Never 2= Rarely 3= Sometimes 4= Often 5= Always			<p>This is a variable that is not in Molgenis. This is a suggestion for harmonisation.</p> <p>7-point likert scale in ABCD -</p>	ABCD, STARS

						potential to collapse some responses into 5 categories	
	Jointactivity_p_r_t	Joint activity with parents	1= often 2= seldom 3= never		categorical	This is a suggestion for harmonisation. Some categories in cohorts may need collapsing to harmonise	ALPINE, FINNTWIN, NORAH
	Family_participation_p_pr_t	Parent knows child's activities/hobbies/interests	1= Never 2= Rarely 3= Sometimes 4= Often 5= Always		categorical	This is a variable that is not in Molgenis. This is a suggestion for harmonisation.	ABCD, FINNTWIN
	Help_Homewk_ch_cr_t	Parent helps child with homework	1= Never 2= Sometimes 3= Often 4= Always		categorical	This is a variable that is not in Molgenis. This is a suggestion for harmonisation.	NORAH, RANCH
Relational dynamics: Social climate/atmosphere							
Harmony/Disharmony	Fam_Harmony_ch_p_t	Child got along well with parents - parents report	1= Never 2= Rarely 3= Sometimes 4= Often 5= very often		categorical	This is a variable that is not in Molgenis. This is a suggestion for harmonisation. FINNTWIN has report on characterist of home atmosphere - perhaps	ALPINE, FINNTWIN, NORAH

						dimension of this can be used to indicate harmony	
	Fam_Harmony_ch_cr_t	Child got along well with parents - child report	1= Never 2= Rarely 3= Sometimes 4= Often 5= very often		categorical	This is a variable that is not in Molgenis. This is a suggestion for harmonisation. FINNTWIN has report on characterist of home atmosphere - perhaps dimension of this can be used to indicate harmony	ALPINE, FINNTWIN, NORA
Quality of relationship	Qlrelations_fam_ch_cr_t	Parents-child relationship - Child feels understood by parents	1= Strongly disagree 2= disagree 3= agree 4= strongly agree		categorical	This is a variable that is not in molgenis. This is a suggestion for harmonisation. **Note variables can respond to relationship with mother/father/siblings	FINNTWIN, STARS
	Qlrelations_fam_ch_p_t	Parent reports good relationship with child/children	1= not true 2= true to some extent 3= very true		categorical	This is a variable that is not in Molgenis. This is a suggestion for harmonisation.	ABCD, FINNTWIN, STARS
	Qlrelations_Peers_ch_cr_t	Satisfaction with friends	1= mainly yes 2= sometimes 3= mainly no 4= not at all		categorical	This is a variable that is not in Molgenis. This is a suggestion for harmonisation. Questions for ALPINE and STARS differ from the domain of satisfaction -	ABCD, ALPINE, FINNTWIN, STARS

						perhaps they can be transformed to be more harmonious?	
	Qltrelations_School_ch_cr_t	Satisfied/feel good in school or with teacher relationship	1= Never 2= Rarely 3= Sometimes 4= Often 5= Always		categorical	This is a variable that is not in Molgenis. This is a suggestion for harmonisation.	FINNTWIN, NORAH, STARS
Adaptive/maladaptive Living conditions							
Change in family structure	Chg_Fam_Divorce_ch_p_t	Parents of the child divorced - parent report	1= yes 2= No		Binary	This is a variable that is not in Molgenis. This is a suggestion for harmonisation. Should these be separated further e.g., indicator for adoption and an indicator for divorce? Or is the experience of a change in family structure enough?	ABCD, BREATHE, PIAMA, W
	Chg_Fam_Divorce_ch_cr_t	Parents of the child divorced - child report	1= yes 2= No			This is a variable that is not in Molgenis. This is a suggestion for harmonisation.	ABCD, FINNTWIN, PIAMA,
	Chg_Fam_Adoption_ch_p_t	The child has been adopted	1= yes 2= No			This is a variable that is not in Molgenis. This is a	ABCD, BREATHE, RANCH, WALNUTS

						suggestion for harmonisation.	
	Chg_Fam_AdoptionAGE_ch_p_t	Age child was adopted	years		continuous	This is a variable that is not in molgenesis. This is a suggestion for harmonisation.	BREATHE, WALNUTS
	Chg_Fam_Death_ch_p_t	Death of close person family member/friend - child report	1= yes 2= No		Binary	This is a variable that is not in molgenesis. This is a suggestion for harmonisation.	ABCD, PIAMA
	Chg_Fam_Death_ch_cr_t	Death of close person family member/friend - child report	1= yes 2= No			This is a variable that is not in molgenesis. This is a suggestion for harmonisation.	ABCD, FINNTWIN,PIAMA,
life threatening experience of child or close person	critical_event_ch_p_t	Has the child experienced a life threatening experience - parent report	1= yes 2= No		Binary	This is a variable that is not in Molgenis. This is a suggestion for harmonisation.	ABCD, PIAMA,
	critical_event_ch_cr_t	Has the child experienced a life threatening experience - child report	1= yes 2= No		Binary	This is a variable that is not in Molgenis. This is a suggestion for harmonisation.	ABCD, FINNTWIN,PIAMA,
	Illness_accident_ch_cr_t	Has the child experienced an illness or accident - child report	1= yes 2= No		Binary	This is a variable that is not in molgenesis. This is a suggestion for harmonisation.	ABCD, FINNTWIN,PIAMA
Change in environment	Chg_residence_ch_pr_t	Has the child moved home - parent report	1= yes 2= No		Binary	This is a variable that is not in Molgenis. This is a	ABCD,ALPINE, FINNTWIN, PIAMA, RANCH_NL, WALN

						suggestion for harmonisation.	
	Chg_residence_ch_cr_t	Has the child moved home - child report	1= yes 2= No		Binary	This is a variable that is not in Molgenis. This is a suggestion for harmonisation.	ABCD, FINNTWINN
	Chg_school_ch_cr_t	Has the child changed schools - child report	1= yes 2= No		Binary	This is a variable that is not in Molgenis. This is a suggestion for harmonisation.	ABCD, FINNTWINN
Bullying / cyberbullying	Bullying_ch_cr_t	Has the child been bullied - child report	1= yes 2= No		Binary	This is a variable that is not in Molgenis. This is a suggestion for harmonisation.	ABCD, PIAMA, STARS, WA
	Bullying_ch_p_t	Has the child been bullied - parent report	1= yes 2= No		Binary	This is a variable that is not in Molgenis. This is a suggestion for harmonisation.	ABCD,BREATHE,RANCH_N
family functioning	EverydayStressor_ch_cr_t	Does the child experience everyday stressors	No=0 Parental conflict =1 report misery=2 custody arrangement =3 unrelenting subjective problems =4 other=5		Categorical	This is a variable that is not in Molgenis. This is a suggestion for harmonisation. Piama has an scale for misery (cutt off to potentially be low cut off)	FINNTWIN, PIAMA

Everyday stressors/challenges: crowding	crowding_ch_p_t	Indicator created by number of rooms/size of home & no people / no children at home			continious	This is a variable that is not in Molgenis. This is a suggestion for harmonisation.	ALPINE,FINNTWIN,NORAH RACH_NL
Everyday stressors: parental depression / anxiety	PostN_DepAnx_m_pr_t	Parental depression/anxiety	1= yes 2= No		Binary	This is a variable that is not in Molgenis. This is a suggestion for harmonisation.	ABCD,FAIR?,PIAMA, WALM
Places							
Places for learning/care	preschool_ch_p_t	Attendance to preschool	1= yes 2= No		binary	Molgenis has a binary variable for if Child attending a day care centre within the first year of life (age range ≥ 0 and < 1 year) - yes/no	ABCD, FINNTWIN,PIAMA
Type of Home	Type_housing_ch_p_t	Type of home	1= House 2=Apartment		Categorical	This is a variable that is not in Molgenis. This is a suggestion for harmonisation.	ALPINE, FINNTWIN, NORAH PIAMA, RANCH_NL
	Size_home_ch_p_t	Size of the home	floor-area of your residence in square meters		Continuous	Not all questions relate to number of rooms e.g., number of people sleeping in childs room. Perhaps not all cohorts can be harmonised	INNTWIN, NORAH have the home. PIAMA, RANCH_NL, STAR
Leisure time	Hobbies_ch_p_t	Child participation in a hobby - parent report	1= yes 2= No		binary	NORAH 5-point scale could be collapsed to binary	ABCD, NORAH, PIAMA?
	Hobbies_ch_cr_t	Child participation in a hobby - child report	1= yes 2= No		Binary	This is a variable that is not in Molgenis. This is a	ABCD, FINNTWIN

						suggestion for harmonisation.	
	Socialising_ch_cr_t	How much time spent socialising	1= daily 2= a few times a week 3= less than once a week 4= never		categorical		FINNTWIN, PIAMA
Neighbourhood social environment	NBHR_Childfriendly_ch_p_r	Neighbourhood environment: children can play outside	1=is not right at all; 2= not exactly right 3= largely right 4 = is exactly right		categorical	This is a variable that is not in Molgenis. This is a suggestion for harmonisation.	ALPINE_NORAH
	NBHR_helpful_ch_p_r	Neighbourhood environment: people are kind/helpful	1=is not right at all; 2= not exactly right 3= largely right 4 = is exactly right		categorical	This is a variable that is not in Molgenis. This is a suggestion for harmonisation.	ALPINE_NORAH
	NBHR_satification_ch_p_r	Neighbourhood environment: like living in the area	1=is not right at all; 2= not exactly right 3= largely			This is a variable that is not in Molgenis. This is a suggestion for harmonisation.	ALPINE, NORAH, PIAMA

			right 4 = is exactly right				
Digital world	PlyVideogame_ch_cr_t	How many days a week playing video games_child report	1=Never 2 = a few times a month 3= a few times a week 3 = every day		categorical	The suggested values are condensed options from the available data	ABCD, ALPINE, FINNTWIN, NORAH, WALNUTS
	Computeruse_ch_cr_t	average amount of time per day on the computer	1= Not at all 2= up to 1 h 3= approx 1- 2 h 4= approx 3-4 5= more than 4 hours)			The suggested values are condensed options from the available data	ABCD, BREATHE,PIAMA,
	Digitalmedia_ch_pr_t	Time child spent using digital media - parent reported	1 = never 2= less than once a week 3= once or twice a week 4= three to four times a week 5= almost everyday			PIAMA reports hours per day	ABCD, BREATHE, PIAMA,

	Mobilephoneuse_ch_cr_t	How many text messages sent per day	1= None 2 = one message per week or less 3 = a few messages a week, but not every day 4 = 1- 4 messages a day 5 = 5 – 9 messages a day 6 = 10 or more messages a day			The question in FINNTWIN combined Email and mobile phone messages	ABCD, FINNTWIN, WALNU
Norms & Values							
Cultural values	Religious_group_ch_cr_t	associated with a religious group	1= yes 2= No		Binary		ABCD, FINNTWIN, PIAMA
	Religious_activity_ch_cr_t	time spent being active in a religious activity	1=Never 2=daily 3=weekly 4=more than weekly		Categorical	FINNTWIN = 6 categories: daily; a few times per week; once per week; once a month; once in 6 months; never. ABCD - hours spent per week Suggestion categories - weekly or never	ABCD, FINNTWIN
	ethn_p_p_t	Ethnic background based on country of origin	1= Western			From Molgenis.	ABCD, PIAMA, RANCH_NL

			2= Non-western 3= Mixed			Western countries include European Union, Andorra, Australia, Canada, Iceland, Liechtenstein, Monaco, New Zealand, Norway, San Marino, Switzerland, USA and Vatican City. Non-western countries include all other countries.	
Social norms							
	OwnTV_ch_cr_t	TV in childs bedroom	1=Yes 2=No		binary	This is a variable that is not in Molgenis. This is a suggestion for harmonisation.	ABCD, NORAH, PIAMA, WA
	OwnComputer_ch_cr_t	Child has own computer	1=Yes 2=No		binary	This is a variable that is not in Molgenis. This is a suggestion for harmonisation.	NORAH, PIAMA,
	OwnMobile_ch_cr_t	Child has own mobile	1=Yes 2=No		binary	This is a variable that is not in Molgenis. This is a suggestion for harmonisation.	ABCD, WALNUTS

Harmonisation table for physical exposome variables

Note: Selection of high-priority items for the physical exposome is still pending.

Note2: The table below currently only includes variables that have been given variable names, hence, items that are still unclear on how to harmonize such as noise can only be found in the separate excel-file "Codebook_Equal-Life_Version 1".

Table 7. Codebook for harmonisation of physical exposome variables							
Indicator	Variable name	Label/description	Values	Unit	Data Type	Further instructions	Mapped by
Air quality outdoor Residential /school/preschool							
Air pollution-residential (PM) (child)	res_PM10_ch_t			micrograms_per_cubic_meter		ABCD also has PM25 and FAIR also has PM1 but cannot be harmonised	ABCD, ALPINE, BREATH, FAIR, FINNTWIN, PIAMA, RANCH
	res_PM2.5_ch_t			micrograms_per_cubic_meter			ABCD, BREATH, PIAMA,
Air pollution-residential (PM) (mother)	res_PM10_mr_t			micrograms_per_cubic_meter		ABCD also has PM25 and FAIR also has PM1 but cannot be harmonised	ABCD, FAIR
Air pollution-residential (NO2)	res_no2_ch_t			micrograms_per_c			ABCD, ALPINE, BREATH, FINNTWIN, PIAMA, RANCH_NL, FAIR

				ubic_met er			
	res_no2_mr_t			microgra ms_per_c ubic_met er			ABCD and FAIR
air pollution- residential(NOX)	res_nox_ch_t			microgra ms_per_c ubic_met er			ABCD, ALPINE, BREATH, PIAMA, RANCH_NL, STARS. WALNUTS
Air pollution-school (NO2)	sch_no2_ch_t			microgra ms_per_c ubic_met er		BREATHE - classroom measurements and PIAMA AND ranch MODELLED address linked to air pollution	BREATH, PIAMA, RANCH
Air pollution- school (black carbon)	sch_BC_ch_r_t			microgra ms_per_c ubic_met er		Breathe - classroom measurements and PIAMA - address linked to air pollution	PIAMA, BREATH
Air pollution- school (PM)	sch_PM10_ch_t			microgra ms_per_c ubic_met er			PIAMA, RANCH
	sch_PM2.5_ch_t			microgra ms_per_c ubic_met er			BREATH, PIAMA

Sound/Noise quality outdoor Residential/school/preschool Outdoor							
<i>Residential Noise pollution Road traffic</i>	RES_RT_Lden_ch_t	Residential road traffic noise for the child - LDEN		A weighted decibel	continuous	Potential to convert laeq24 to LDEN RANCH, could potentially use the conversion coefficient from M. Brink et al. 2017 http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2017.10.003 :	ABCD, ALPINE, BREATHE, NORAH, PIAMA, WALNUTS, FAIR RANCH (to be converted from laeq24 to LDEN)
	RES_RT_Lden_mr_t	Residential road traffic noise for the mother - LDEN		A weighted decibel	continuous		ABCD, FAIR
<i>Residential noise pollution rail traffic</i>	RES_RW_Lden_ch_t	Residential railway noise for the child - LDEN		A weighted decibel	continuous	<i>Only FAIR has rail traffic during pregnancy</i> <i>PIAMA and NORAH have for older age groups - unsure if this variable can be harmonised</i>	FAIR, PIAMA, NORAH
<i>Residential noise pollution Air traffic</i>	RES_AIR_Lden_ch_t	Residential air traffic noise for the child - LDEN		A weighted decibel	continuous	FAIR and NORAH have Lden. RANCH has Leaq could be transformed into Lden? PIAMA has a self report of noise	RANCH, FAIR, PIAMA, NORAH

						annoyance/perception/ appraisal	
<i>School Noise pollution Road traffic</i>	<i>sch_RT_lday_ch_t</i>	School road traffic noise for the child - LDay		A weighted decibel?	continuous	<i>NORAH = LPAF,eq,A could this be converted to lday?</i>	ALPINE, BREATHE,
	<i>sch_RT_laeq_ch_t</i>	School road traffic noise for the child - Laeq		A weighted decibel	continuous	<i>Could this be converted to lday?</i>	RANCH + BREATHE (ALSO HAS LDEN)
<i>Residential noise pollution Air traffic</i>	<i>SCH_AIR_laeq9_15 _ch_t</i>	School air traffic noise for the child - Laeq		A weighted decibel	continuous		
Passive smoking							
Mother smoking during pregnancy	<i>preg_smk_m_r_t</i>	Any maternal smoking during pregnancy	0=no 1=yes		binary		ABCD, ALPINE, BREATHE, FAIR, FINNTWIN, WALNUTS
Child passive smoking	<i>smk_exp_ch_r_t</i>	Any exposure to smoking (mother, biological father, social father, any smokers close to the child, or exposure to smoke in the home)	0=no 1=yes		binary		ABCD,ALPINE, BREATHE, FINNTWIN, PIAMA, WALNUTS

Indoor environmental quality at home /school/preschool (moulds/dust/dampness/overall)							
Dampness – residential	res_damp_ch_r_t	any dampness, mould, mildew, humidity water damage at home	0=no 1=yes		binary	This is a variable that is not in Molgenis. This is a suggestion for harmonisation.	ABCD, APLINE, FINNTWIN, PIAMA, RANCH_NL
Crowding Residential /Preschool and school							
Crowding – residential	res_crowding_ch_p_t	population density at home		people_per_square_meter	continuous		ALPINE, FINNTWIN, NORAH, PIAMA, RANCH_NL
Crowding - school	sch_crowding_ch_r_t	population density at classroom		<i>Number of students in one classroom</i>	integer	<i>We do not have info regarding the no. of square meters</i>	FINNTWIN, NORAH
Access to green space (residential. Preschool, school, “en route”)							

Green space – residential	<i>res_GS_NDVI_100_ch_t</i>	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)	ranging from -1 to 1		Continuous		ABCD, ALPINE, BREATHE, PIAMA,
	<i>res_GS_NDVI_300_ch_t</i>	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)	ranging from -1 to 1		Continuous		ABCD, ALPINE, PIAMA,
	<i>res_GS_NDVI_500_ch_t</i>	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)	ranging from -1 to 1		Continuous		ABCD, ALPINE, PIAMA,
	<i>res_GS_NDVI_1000_ch_t</i>	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)	ranging from -1 to 1		Continuous	PIAMA also has 3000m	ALPINE, FAIR, PIAMA
	<i>res_GS_NDVI_1000_mr_t</i>	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)	ranging from -1 to 1		Continuous	ABCD also has data on 100m, 300m and 500	ABCD, FAIR

	<i>res_GS_Use_ch_t</i>	How often to green area	Number of days (average) per year		integer	Suggestion for harmonisation average number of days per month/year/season? But unsure of the response options in PIAMA	BREATHE, and PIAMA
	<i>res_GS_Dis_ch_t</i>	occurrence of green space ≤ 1km from the residential address for child	No=0 yes=1		Binary		ABCD, ALPINE, FAIR, PIAMA
	<i>res_GS_Dis_mr_t</i>	occurrence of green space ≤ 1km from the residential address for mother	No=0 yes=1		Binary		ABCD, FAIR
Green space – school	<i>sch_GS_NDVI_100_ch_t</i>	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)	ranging from -1 to 1		Continuous	ALPINE also has school data for buffers at 250m, 500m, 1000m	ALPINE, BREATHE
Access to blue space (residential. Preschool, school, en route)							
Blue space – residential	<i>res_blue_ch_r_t</i>	occurrence of blue space ≤ 1km from the residential address for child	No=0 yes=1		Binary	BREATHE has Use of blue space but cannot be harmonised with the other cohorts	ABCD, FAIR and PIAMA

						If possible, the blue space should be larger than 0.5 ha	
	res_blue_mr_r_t	occurrence of blue space ≤ 1km from the residential address for mother	No=0 yes=1		Binary	If possible, the blue space should be larger than 0.5 ha	ABCD and FAIR
Smoking							
Child smoking	any_smk_ch_r_t	child smoking (any)	0=no 1=yes		categorical	We can also have child current smoking status (smk-curr). Molgenis has answering options " Non smoker = 1, Occasional smoker = 2, Regular smoker = 3". We can have another variable as "ever smoke"	ABCD, FINNTWIN, PIAMA, STARS, WALNUTS
Age starting to smoking	smoke_begin-ch_r_t	Age when taking up smoking		year	continuous		ABCD,FINNTWIN, PIAMA, WALNUTS
Smoking no. of cigarettes	smk_cig_ch_r_t	Smoking, Number of Cigarettes (Average number of cigarettes smoked per day)	0=none, <10 per day = 1, > or equal to 10 per day = 2.		categorical		ABCD, FINNTWIN, PIAMA, WALNUTS
Substance use							
Alcohol	alc_ch_r_t	child alcohol drinking	0=no 1=yes		categorical	This is a variable that is not in Molgenis. This is a suggestion for harmonization.	ABCD, FINNTWIN, PIAMA, STARS, WALNUT
Drugs	drug_ch_r_t	child usage of drug	0=no 1=yes		categorical	This is a variable that is not in Molgenis. This is a	ABCD, FINNTWIN, PIAMA, STARS, WALNUT

						suggestion for harmonization.	
Food: healthy food intake, breast feeding							
Breast feeding	breastfed_any_ch_r_t	Total duration of any breastfeeding (in the index child), in months			continuous	BREATHE is the only categorical cohort. Should we create a categorical variable instead based on BREATHE. Molgenesis has a continuous variable.	ABCD, ALPINE, BREATHE, FINNTWIN?, PIAMA, WALNUTS
Fruit intake	Fruit_cat_ch_r_t	How often does the child/do you eat fresh fruit?	Daily = 1 Weekly = 2 Seldom = 3 Never = 4 N/A = -99?		categorical	Molgenis has another variable formulated as: How much fresh fruit do you eat?(Gram_per_day)	ABCD,ALPINE, FINNTWIN, PIAMA,WALNUTS
Vegetable intake	Totveg_cat_ch_r_t	How often does the child/do you eat vegetables?	Daily = 1 Weekly = 2 Seldom = 3 Never = 4 N/A = -99?			Molgenis has variable for consumption of "raw vegetables" - consider that and separate raw and cooked vegetables? Should we have a separate variable for potatoes?	ABCD, ALPINE, FINNTWIN, PIAMA, WALNUTS
Snack intake	Snacks_cat_ch_r_t	How often does the child/do you consume salty or sugary snacks and fast food (e.g. chips, sweets or cakes)?	Daily = 1 Weekly = 2 Seldom = 3 Never = 4		categorical	Should we separate sugary snacks from fast food?	ABCD, ALPINE, FINNTWIN, PIAMA, WALNUTS

			N/A = - 99?				
Dietary supplemental intake	supp_ch_r_t	Any Dietary Supplements Intake in children	No=0 yes=1		binary	Should we be more specific about the type of supplement? Like which vitamin?	PIAMA, WALNUTS
Intake of sweet drinks	sweet_drinks_cat_ch_r_t	Intake of sugary drinks (How often does the child/do you consume fat or sugary drinks (e.g. coke or similar))	Daily = 1 Weekly = 2 Seldom = 3 Never = 4 N/A = - 99?		categorical	Should we be more specific about the type of drink? like light drinks/soft drinks/natural fruits ...? Several studies have the option of milk/butter milk, perhaps we should add milk and butter milk to the dairy products	ABCD, ALPINE, FINNTWIN, PIAMA, WALNUTS
Specific food groups	<i>Not yet finalized – can be harmonized on a needs-basis</i>						
Food allergy/intolerance	Foodall_ch_r_t	any food allergy/intolerance					BREATHE, PIAMA, WALNUTS
Birth outcomes							
Low birth weight	birth_weight_ch_r_t			gram	continuous	We can also have categorical variable as low birth weight yes/no	<i>Not yet mapped out</i>
Small for gestational age	weight_who_ga_ch_r_t	WHO size for gestational age	SGA=1 AGA=2 LGA=3			Instruction: Weight of the child for gestational age at birth, categorised into small for gestational age (SGA), appropriate for gestational age (AGA) and large for gestational age (LGA). Defined using the WHO foetal growth charts (Kiserud et al 2017) using the 5th and 95th	<i>Not yet mapped out</i>

						percentiles as cut-off values for SGA and LGA respectively. A child is classified as SGA if their birth weight is \leq 5th percentile for their gestational age (in completed weeks). A child is classified as LGA if their birth weight is \geq 95th percentile for their gestational age (in completed weeks).	
Preterm birth	preterm_ch_r_t	child born preterm	No=0 yes=1		binary	This is a variable that is not in Molgenis. This is a suggestion for harmonization. Instruction: Preterm is defined as babies born alive before 37 weeks of pregnancy are completed.	<i>Not yet mapped out</i>

Harmonisation table for mediator variables

Note: Selection of high-priority items for the mediators is still pending.

Table 7. Codebook for harmonisation of mediator variables							
Concept	Variable name	Label/description	Values	Unit	Data Type	Further instructions	Mapped by
Sleep quality/insomnia	sleep_quality_insomnia_ch_cr_t	Child reported sleep quality and insomnia	<i>Not yet specified</i>			<i>Consult sleep-team</i>	RANCH, ABCD, ALPINE, PIAMA, STARS, FINNTWIN, NORAH?
Sleep duration	sleep_duration_ch_cr_t	Child reported sleep duration	<i>Not yet specified</i>			<i>Consult sleep-team</i>	ABCD, WALNUTS, PIAMA, STARS
Stress	Stressful_event_ch_cr_t	Child reported critical /stressful life event	Sumscore of life events		Discrete	The ABCD cohort also has questions on how long the child has suffered from an event. To use this information - weight each event/risk with "how-long" score to assess	PIAMA, STARS, FINNTWIN, ABCD

						<p>severeness of the event. Then sum up weighted risks. If the total value gets too high, calculate $\log(\text{risk} \times \text{weight})$.</p> <p>- information from the document "Harmonisation of variables on stress and coping/self-regulation" Klatte et al.,</p>	
	Stressful_event_ch_pr_t	Parent reported critical /stressful life event	Sumscore of life events		Discrete	<p>From the document "Harmonisation of variables on stress and coping/self-regulation" Klatte et al.</p>	PIAMA, ABCD
	Percieved_Stress_ch_cr_t	Percieved stress child report	Sumscore of percieved/felt stress		Discrete	<p>From the document "Harmonisation of variables on stress and</p>	RANCH, PIAMA, STARS, FINNTWINN, ABCD

						<p>coping/self-regulation" Klatte et al.</p>	
	Percieved_restorativeQLT_ch_cr_t	Percieved restorative quality child reported	<p>For random forest and regression: combined mean scores for outdoors and indoors</p> <p>For SEM: use single items referring to 2 latent constructs (outdoors/indoors)</p>		continuous	<p>From the document "Harmonisation of variables on stress and coping/self-regulation" Klatte et al.</p> <p>Note: in PIAMA the response options change based on the question</p>	NORAH, RANCH, PIAMA, ALPINE
	Annoyance_noise_ch_cr_t	Noise annoyance child reported	<p>check in factor analysis; transform to standardised score (z-score), calculate mean Z-score. Combine to mean score</p>		continuous	<p>From the document "Harmonisation of variables on stress and coping/self-regulation" Klatte et al.</p> <p>Note: RANCH is the only cohort to ask about annoyance</p>	NORAH, RANCH, PIAMA, ALPINE

						seperatly at home and school NORAH has additional items but only use those on road traffic noise	
	Annoyance_noise_pr_pr_t	Noise annoyance child reported	Combine to mean score		continuous	From the document "Harmonisation of variables on stress and coping/self-regulation" Klatte et al.	NORAH, BREATE, ALPINE
	Interference_noise_ch_cr_t	Noise interferences/disturbances_child reported	Combine to mean score		continuous	From the document "Harmonisation of variables on stress and coping/self-regulation" Klatte et al.	NORAH, RANCH, ALPINE

References

1. Mònica López Vicente JJ, Raquel Garcia, Silvia Fernandez and Jordi Sunyer. Life Cycle WP6 Harmonization Manual. Rotterdam, Netherlands: Erasmus MC; 2019.
2. van der Velde KJ, Imhann F, Charbon B, Pang C, van Enkevort D, Slofstra M, et al. MOLGENIS Research: Advanced bioinformatics data software for non-bioinformaticians. *Bioinformatics*. 2019;35(6):1076-8.

Table displaying enrichment variables (physical and social) from Batch 1 (summer/fall 2022)				
Note the variable names need to be harmonised thus once the correct year for the enrichment data is included in your cohort please then remove the year from the indicator name e.g., <i>dist_green_ua_2006</i> will be <i>dist_green_ua</i>				
Variables - Conceptual	Indicator	Variable name	Definition	Unit/Data type
PHYSICAL ENRICHMENT				
<i>TUD Enrichment</i>				
		id	Original id of each geo-coordinate provided by the cohort owners.	
Street network variables		nearest_street_betweenness	The betweenness score of the nearest street segment to each geo-coordinate.	
		wavg_street_betweenness_{100,300}m	The average street betweenness scores of every street segment within 100m or 300m from each geo-coordinate weighted according to the street segment's length.	
		nearest_street_sinusosity	The sinusosity score of the nearest street segment to each geo-coordinate.	
		wavg_street_sinusosity_{100,300}m	The average street sinusosity scores of every street segment within 100m or 300m from each geo-coordinate weighted according to the street segment's length.	
		mean_intersection_closeness_{100,300}m	The mean street intersection closeness scores of every street segment within 100m or 300m from each geo-coordinate.	
		nearest_street_length	The length of the nearest street segment to each geo-coordinate.	
		nearest_street_width	The width of the nearest street segment to each geo-coordinate (NB: some values are missing)	
		nearest_street_maxspeed	The maximum speed limit of the nearest street segment to each geo-coordinate. (NB: some values are missing)	

		nearest_street_highway	The type of the nearest street segment to each geo-coordinate. (e.g., living street, cycleway, residential)	
		nearest_street_lanes	The number of lanes of the nearest street segment to each geo-coordinate. (NB: some values are missing)	
		nearest_street_dist	The distance between each geo-coordinate and the nearest street segment.	
Greenspace accessibility variables		_bool_{type}_within{distance}m	Whether or not there are greenspaces/normal parks/pocket parks within walking distance from the geo-coordinate.	
		count{type}_within{distance}m	The count of greenspaces/normal parks/pocket parks within walking distance from the geo-coordinate.	
		meanarea{type}_within{distance}m	The mean area of all interconnected greenspaces/normal parks/pocket parks within walking distance from the geo-coordinate, including greenspace areas partly within walking distance while further extending beyond walking distance.	
		medianarea{type}_within{distance}m	The median area of all interconnected greenspaces/normal parks/pocket parks within walking distance from the geo-coordinate, including greenspace areas partly within walking distance while further extending beyond walking distance.	
		minarea{type}_within{distance}m	The area of the smallest interconnected area of greenspaces/normal parks/pocket parks within walking distance from the geo-coordinate.	
		maxarea{type}_within{distance}m	The area of the largest interconnected area of greenspaces/normal parks/pocket parks within walking distance from the geo-coordinate.	

		sumarea{type}_within{distance}m	The total area of all interconnected greenspaces/normal parks/pocket parks within walking distance from the geo-coordinate, including greenspace areas partly within walking distance while further extending beyond walking distance.	
Sidewalk width variables		wavg_sidewalk_width_{100, 300}m	Average width of all sidewalks intersecting a circular buffer zone of 100 or 300 metres respectively around the geo-coordinate. Average width is weighted according to length of sidewalk segment, thereby attributing higher value to long sidewalks. Intersecting sidewalks that extend beyond the buffer zone area are taken into account with their full lengths.	
ISGlobal enrichment				
		gid		None
		GEOCODE	The geocode fields originally provided for the cohort (eg: plid, initialyear, endyear, object...) which allows for unique identification of the geocodes.	
		GISCO_ID	The code that uniquely identifies each municipal unit from the LAU layer.	
		LAU_NAME	The municipality name from the LAU layer.	
Building		built_ESM_100_2012	Percentage (%) of built up area within a buffer area of 100m radius around geocode. ,2012	Percentage (0 - 100%)
		built_ESM_100_2015	Percentage (%) of built up area within a buffer area of 100m radius around geocode. ,2015	Percentage (0 - 100%)
		built_ESM_300_2012	Percentage (%) of built up area within a buffer area of 300m radius around geocode. ,2012	Percentage (0 - 100%)
		built_ESM_300_2015	Percentage (%) of built up area within a buffer area of 300m radius around geocode. ,2015	Percentage (0 - 100%)

		built_ESM_500_2012	Percentage (%) of built up area within a buffer area of 500m radius around geocode. ,2012	Percentage (0 - 100%)
		built_ESM_500_2015	Percentage (%) of built up area within a buffer area of 500m radius around geocode. ,2015	Percentage (0 - 100%)
		built_GHS_100_1990	Percentage (%) of built up area within a buffer area of 100m radius around geocode. ,1990	Percentage (0 - 100%)
		built_GHS_100_2000	Percentage (%) of built up area within a buffer area of 100m radius around geocode. ,2000	Percentage (0 - 100%)
		built_GHS_100_2014	Percentage (%) of built up area within a buffer area of 100m radius around geocode. ,2014	Percentage (0 - 100%)
		built_GHS_300_1990	Percentage (%) of built up area within a buffer area of 300m radius around geocode. ,1990	Percentage (0 - 100%)
		built_GHS_300_2000	Percentage (%) of built up area within a buffer area of 300m radius around geocode. ,2000	Percentage (0 - 100%)
		built_GHS_300_2014	Percentage (%) of built up area within a buffer area of 300m radius around geocode. ,2014	Percentage (0 - 100%)
		built_GHS_500_1990	Percentage (%) of built up area within a buffer area of 500m radius around geocode. ,1990	Percentage (0 - 100%)
		built_GHS_500_2000	Percentage (%) of built up area within a buffer area of 500m radius around geocode. ,2000	Percentage (0 - 100%)
		built_GHS_500_2014	Percentage (%) of built up area within a buffer area of 500m radius around geocode. ,2014	Percentage (0 - 100%)
		built_ISA_100_2006	Percentage (%) of impervious area within a buffer area of 100m radius around geocode. ,2006	Percentage (1 - 100%)
		built_ISA_100_2009	Percentage (%) of impervious area within a buffer area of 100m radius around geocode. ,2009	Percentage (1 - 100%)

		built_ISA_100_2012	Percentage (%) of impervious area within a buffer area of 100m radius around geocode. ,2012	Percentage (1 - 100%)
		built_ISA_100_2015	Percentage (%) of impervious area within a buffer area of 100m radius around geocode. ,2015	Percentage (1 - 100%)
		built_ISA_100_2018	Percentage (%) of impervious area within a buffer area of 100m radius around geocode. ,2018	Percentage (1 - 100%)
		built_ISA_300_2006	Percentage (%) of impervious area within a buffer area of 300m radius around geocode. ,2006	Percentage (1 - 100%)
		built_ISA_300_2009	Percentage (%) of impervious area within a buffer area of 300m radius around geocode. ,2009	Percentage (1 - 100%)
		built_ISA_300_2012	Percentage (%) of impervious area within a buffer area of 300m radius around geocode. ,2012	Percentage (1 - 100%)
		built_ISA_300_2015	Percentage (%) of impervious area within a buffer area of 300m radius around geocode. ,2015	Percentage (1 - 100%)
		built_ISA_300_2018	Percentage (%) of impervious area within a buffer area of 300m radius around geocode. ,2018	Percentage (1 - 100%)
		built_ISA_500_2006	Percentage (%) of impervious area within a buffer area of 500m radius around geocode. ,2006	Percentage (1 - 100%)
		built_ISA_500_2009	Percentage (%) of impervious area within a buffer area of 500m radius around geocode. ,2009	Percentage (1 - 100%)
		built_ISA_500_2012	Percentage (%) of impervious area within a buffer area of 500m radius around geocode. ,2012	Percentage (1 - 100%)
		built_ISA_500_2015	Percentage (%) of impervious area within a buffer area of 500m radius around geocode. ,2015	Percentage (1 - 100%)
		built_ISA_500_2018	Percentage (%) of impervious area within a buffer area of 500m radius around geocode. ,2018	Percentage (1 - 100%)

Green and blue spaces		dist_green_ua_2006	Euclidean distance to closer green space. Land use categories for green: ('14100','14200','20000', '30000', '40000'). Using UA. ,2006	Meters (m)
		size_green_ua_2006	Area of the closer green space. Using UA. ,2006	Square meters (m2)
		item_green_ua_2006	Land use category of closer green space. Using UA. ,2006	Categorical: Land use category
		dist_blue_ua_2006	Euclidean distance to closer blue space. Land use categories for blue: ('50000'). Using UA. ,2006	Meters (m)
		size_blue_ua_2006	Area of the closer blue space. Using UA. ,2006	Square meters (m2)
		item_blue_ua_2006	Land use category of closer blue space. Using UA. ,2006	Categorical: Land use category
		dist_major_green_ua_2006	Euclidean distance to closer major green space. Land use categories for green: ('14100','14200','20000', '30000', '40000'). Major means >5000m2. Using UA. ,2006	Meters (m)
		size_major_green_ua_2006	Area of the closer green space. Major means >5000m2. Using UA. ,2006	Square meters (m2)
		item_major_green_ua_2006	Land use category of closer major green space. Major means >5000m2. Using UA. ,2006	Categorical: Land use category
		dist_major_blue_ua_2006	Euclidean distance to closer blue space. Land use categories for blue: ('50000'). Major means >5000m2. Using UA. ,2006	Meters (m)
		size_major_blue_ua_2006	Area of the closer blue space. Major means >5000m2. Using UA. ,2006	Square meters (m2)
		item_major_blue_ua_2006	Land use category of closer major blue space. Major means >5000m2. Using UA. ,2006	Categorical: Land use category
		int_ua_2006	Geocode within Urban Atlas 2006 coverage area (1 = yes, 0 = no). ,2006	Boolean (1 = yes, 0 = no)

		dist_green_ua_2012	Euclidean distance to closer green space. Land use categories for green: ('14100', '14200', '21000', '22000', '23000', '24000', '25000', '31000', '32000', '40000'). Using UA. ,2012	Meters (m)
		size_green_ua_2012	Area of the closer green space. Using UA. ,2012	Square meters (m2)
		item_green_ua_2012	Land use category of closer green space. Using UA. ,2012	Categorical: Land use category
		dist_blue_ua_2012	Euclidean distance to closer blue space. Land use categories for blue: ('50000'). Using UA. ,2012	meters
		size_blue_ua_2012	Area of the closer blue space. Using UA. ,2012	Square meters (m2)
		item_blue_ua_2012	Land use category of closer blue space. Using UA. ,2012	Categorical: Land use category
		dist_major_green_ua_2012	Euclidean distance to closer major green space. Land use categories for green: ('14100', '14200', '21000', '22000', '23000', '24000', '25000', '31000', '32000', '40000'). Major means >5000m2. Using UA. ,2012	Meters (m)
		size_major_green_ua_2012	Area of the closer green space. Major means >5000m2. Using UA. ,2012	Square meters (m2)
		item_major_green_ua_2012	Land use category of closer major green space. Major means >5000m2. Using UA. ,2012	Categorical: Land use category
		dist_major_blue_ua_2012	Euclidean distance to closer blue space. Land use categories for blue: ('50000'). Major means >5000m2. Using UA. ,2012	Meters (m)
		size_major_blue_ua_2012	Area of the closer blue space. Major means >5000m2. Using UA. ,2012	Square meters (m2)
		item_major_blue_ua_2012	Land use category of closer major blue space. Major means >5000m2. Using UA. ,2012	Categorical: Land use category
		int_ua_2012	Geocode within Urban Atlas 2012 coverage area (1 = yes, 0 = no). ,2012	Boolean (1 = yes, 0 = no)

		dist_green_ua_2018	Euclidean distance to closer green space. Land use categories for green: ('14100','14200','21000', '22000', '23000', '24000','25000', '31000', '32000', '40000'). Using UA. ,2018	Meters (m)
		size_green_ua_2018	Area of the closer green space. Using UA. ,2018	Square meters (m2)
		item_green_ua_2018	Land use category of closer green space. Using UA. ,2018	Categorical: Land use category
		dist_blue_ua_2018	Euclidean distance to closer blue space. Land use categories for blue: ('50000'). Using UA. ,2018	Meters (m)
		size_blue_ua_2018	Area of the closer blue space. Using UA. ,2018	Square meters (m2)
		item_blue_ua_2018	Land use category of closer blue space. Using UA. ,2018	Categorical: Land use category
		dist_major_green_ua_2018	Euclidean distance to closer major green space. Land use categories for green: ('14100','14200','21000', '22000', '23000', '24000','25000', '31000', '32000', '40000'). Major means >5000m2. Using UA. ,2018	Meters (m)
		size_major_green_ua_2018	Area of the closer green space. Major means >5000m2. Using UA. ,2018	Square meters (m2)
		item_major_green_ua_2018	Land use category of closer major green space. Major means >5000m2. Using UA. ,2018	Categorical: Land use category
		dist_major_blue_ua_2018	Euclidean distance to closer blue space. Land use categories for blue: ('50000'). Major means >5000m2. Using UA. ,2018	Meters (m)
		size_major_blue_ua_2018	Area of the closer blue space. Major means >5000m2. Using UA. ,2018	Square meters (m2)
		item_major_blue_ua_2018	Land use category of closer major blue space. Major means >5000m2. Using UA. ,2018	Categorical: Land use category
		int_ua_2018	Geocode within Urban Atlas 2018 coverage area (1 = yes, 0 = no). ,2018	Boolean (1 = yes, 0 = no)

		dist_green_clc_2000	Euclidean distance to closer green space. Land use categories for green: ('141', '142', '211', '212', '213', '221', '222', '223', '231', '241', '242', '243', '244', '311', '312', '313', '321', '322', '323', '324', '333', '334', '335', '411', '412', '421'). Using CLC. ,2000	Meters (m)
		size_green_clc_2000	Area of the closer green space. Using CLC. ,2000	Square meters (m2)
		item_green_clc_2000	Land use category of closer green space. Using CLC. ,2000	Categorical: Land use category
		dist_blue_clc_2000	Euclidean distance to closer blue space. Land use categories for blue: ('331', '421', '422', '423', '511', '512', '521', '522', '523'). Using CLC. ,2000	Meters (m)
		size_blue_clc_2000	Area of the closer blue space. Using CLC. ,2000	Square meters (m2)
		item_blue_clc_2000	Land use category of closer blue. Using CLC. ,2000	Categorical: Land use category
		dist_green_clc_2006	Euclidean distance to closer green space. Land use categories for green: ('141', '142', '211', '212', '213', '221', '222', '223', '231', '241', '242', '243', '244', '311', '312', '313', '321', '322', '323', '324', '333', '334', '335', '411', '412'). Using CLC. ,2006	Meters (m)
		size_green_clc_2006	Area of the closer green space. Using CLC. ,2006	Square meters (m2)
		item_green_clc_2006	Land use category of closer green space. Using CLC. ,2006	Categorical: Land use category
		dist_blue_clc_2006	Euclidean distance to closer blue space. Land use categories for blue: ('331', '421', '422', '423', '511', '512', '521', '522', '523'). Using CLC. ,2006	Meters (m)
		size_blue_clc_2006	Area of the closer blue space. Using CLC. ,2006	Square meters (m2)
		item_blue_clc_2006	Land use category of closer blue. Using CLC. ,2006	Categorical: Land use category

		dist_green_clc_2012	Euclidean distance to closer green space. Land use categories for green: ('141', '142', '211', '212', '213', '221', '222', '223', '231', '241', '242', '243', '244', '311', '312', '313', '321', '322', '323', '324', '333', '334', '335', '411', '412'). Using CLC. ,2012	Meters (m)
		size_green_clc_2012	Area of the closer green space. Using CLC. ,2012	Square meters (m2)
		item_green_clc_2012	Land use category of closer green space. Using CLC. ,2012	Categorical: Land use category
		dist_blue_clc_2012	Euclidean distance to closer blue space. Land use categories for blue: ('331', '421', '422', '423', '511', '512', '521', '522', '523'). Using CLC. ,2012	Meters (m)
		size_blue_clc_2012	Area of the closer blue space. Using CLC. ,2012	Square meters (m2)
		item_blue_clc_2012	Land use category of closer blue. Using CLC. ,2012	Categorical: Land use category
		dist_green_clc_2018	Euclidean distance to closer green space. Land use categories for green: ('141', '142', '211', '212', '213', '221', '222', '223', '231', '241', '242', '243', '244', '311', '312', '313', '321', '322', '323', '324', '333', '334', '335', '411', '412'). Using CLC. ,2018	Meters (m)
		size_green_clc_2018	Area of the closer green space. Using CLC. ,2018	Square meters (m2)
		item_green_clc_2018	Land use category of closer green space. Using CLC. ,2018	Categorical: Land use category
		dist_blue_clc_2018	Euclidean distance to closer blue space. Land use categories for blue: ('331', '421', '422', '423', '511', '512', '521', '522', '523'). Using CLC. ,2018	Meters (m)
		size_blue_clc_2018	Area of the closer blue space. Using CLC. ,2018	Square meters (m2)
		item_blue_clc_2018	Land use category of closer blue. Using CLC. ,2018	Categorical: Land use category

		access_green_ua_300_2006	Access to a major green spaces, ie. presence of a major green space within 300m from geocode (euclidean distance), where 1 = yes (accessible); 0 = no (not accessible). Using UA. ,2006	Boolean (1 = yes, 0 = no, NA = geocode outside of Urban Atlas)
		access_green_ua_300_2012	Access to a major green spaces, ie. presence of a major green space within 300m from geocode (euclidean distance), where 1 = yes (accessible); 0 = no (not accessible). Using UA. ,2012	Boolean (1 = yes, 0 = no, NA = geocode outside of Urban Atlas)
		access_green_ua_300_2018	Access to a major green spaces, ie. presence of a major green space within 300m from geocode (euclidean distance), where 1 = yes (accessible); 0 = no (not accessible). Using UA. ,2018	Boolean (1 = yes, 0 = no, NA = geocode outside of Urban Atlas)
		access_blue_ua_300_2006	Access to a major blue spaces, ie. presence of a major blue space within 300m from geocode (euclidean distance), where 1 = yes (accessible); 0 = no (not accessible). Using UA. ,2006	Boolean (1 = yes, 0 = no, NA = geocode outside of Urban Atlas)
		access_blue_ua_300_2012	Access to a major blue spaces, ie. presence of a major blue space within 300m from geocode (euclidean distance), where 1 = yes (accessible); 0 = no (not accessible). Using UA. ,2012	Boolean (1 = yes, 0 = no, NA = geocode outside of Urban Atlas)
		access_blue_ua_300_2018	Access to a major blue spaces, ie. presence of a major blue space within 300m from geocode (euclidean distance), where 1 = yes (accessible); 0 = no (not accessible). Using UA. ,2018	Boolean (1 = yes, 0 = no, NA = geocode outside of Urban Atlas)
Land use		urbanhigh_100_2006	Percentage of high density residential land use type within a 100 meter around geocode. ,2006	Ratio from 0 to 1
		urbanlow_100_2006	Percentage of low density residential land use type within a 100 meter around geocode. ,2006	Ratio from 0 to 1
		com_ind_100_2006	Percentage of commercial and industrial land use type within a 100 meter around geocode. ,2006	Ratio from 0 to 1
		infrast_100_2006	Percentage of infrastructures land use type within a 100 meter around geocode. ,2006	Ratio from 0 to 1

		green_urb_100_2006	Percentage of urban green land use type within a 100 meter around geocode. ,2006	Ratio from 0 to 1
		agric_100_2006	Percentage of agricultural land use type within a 100 meter around geocode. ,2006	Ratio from 0 to 1
		natural_100_2006	Percentage of natural land use type within a 100 meter around geocode. ,2006	Ratio from 0 to 1
		water_100_2006	Percentage of water land use type within a 100 meter around geocode. ,2006	Ratio from 0 to 1
		other_100_2006	Percentage of other land use type within a 100 meter around geocode. ,2006	Ratio from 0 to 1
		no_data_100_2006	Percentage of No Data land use type within a 100 meter around geocode. This are areas covered by clouds that were not able to classify to a particular land use. Not considered to create LUM. ,2006	Ratio from 0 to 1
		sumarea_100_2006	Sum of different land uses available within buffer area. This is to check wether the land use data covers the buffer area or not. ,2006	Ratio from 0 to 1
		in_ua_2006	The geocode is within the Urban Atlas layer (1 = yes, 0 = no). ,2006	Boolean (1 = yes, 0 = no)
		lum_100_2006	Land Use Mix index within a buffer area of 100 meters around geocode. Unitless, from 0 to 1, where 0 represents a single land use in the parcels and 1 represents a perfect balance of all Land Use in the parcels. ,2006	Unitless, from 0 to 1, where 1 indicates mixture of landuses and 0 homogeneity of landuse
		urbanhigh_300_2006	Percentage of high density residential land use type within a 300 meter around geocode. ,2006	Ratio from 0 to 1

		urbanlow_300_2006	Percentage of low density residential land use type within a 300 meter around geocode. ,2006	Ratio from 0 to 1
		com_ind_300_2006	Percentage of commercial and industrial land use type within a 300 meter around geocode. ,2006	Ratio from 0 to 1
		infrast_300_2006	Percentage of infrastructures land use type within a 300 meter around geocode. ,2006	Ratio from 0 to 1
		green_urb_300_2006	Percentage of urban green land use type within a 300 meter around geocode. ,2006	Ratio from 0 to 1
		agric_300_2006	Percentage of agricultural land use type within a 300 meter around geocode. ,2006	Ratio from 0 to 1
		natural_300_2006	Percentage of natural land use type within a 300 meter around geocode. ,2006	Ratio from 0 to 1
		water_300_2006	Percentage of water land use type within a 300 meter around geocode. ,2006	Ratio from 0 to 1
		other_300_2006	Percentage of other land use type within a 300 meter around geocode. ,2006	Ratio from 0 to 1
		no_data_300_2006	Percentage of No Data land use type within a 300 meter around geocode. This are areas covered by clouds that were not able to classify to a particular land use. Not considered to create LUM. ,2006	Ratio from 0 to 1
		sumarea_300_2006	Sum of different land uses available within buffer area. This is to check wether the land use data covers the buffer area or not. ,2006	Ratio from 0 to 1
		lum_300_2006	Land Use Mix index within a buffer area of 300 meters around geocode. Unitless, from 0 to 1, where 0 represents a single land use in the parcels and 1 represents a perfect balance of all Land Use in the parcels. ,2006	Unitless, from 0 to 1, where 1 indicates mixture of landuses and 0 homogeneity of landuse

		urbanhigh_500_2006	Percentage of high density residential land use type within a 500 meter around geocode. ,2006	Ratio from 0 to 1
		urbanlow_500_2006	Percentage of low density residential land use type within a 500 meter around geocode. ,2006	Ratio from 0 to 1
		com_ind_500_2006	Percentage of commercial and industrial land use type within a 500 meter around geocode. ,2006	Ratio from 0 to 1
		infrast_500_2006	Percentage of infrastructures land use type within a 500 meter around geocode. ,2006	Ratio from 0 to 1
		green_urb_500_2006	Percentage of urban green land use type within a 500 meter around geocode. ,2006	Ratio from 0 to 1
		agric_500_2006	Percentage of agricultural land use type within a 500 meter around geocode. ,2006	Ratio from 0 to 1
		natural_500_2006	Percentage of natural land use type within a 500 meter around geocode. ,2006	Ratio from 0 to 1
		water_500_2006	Percentage of water land use type within a 500 meter around geocode. ,2006	Ratio from 0 to 1
		other_500_2006	Percentage of other land use type within a 500 meter around geocode. ,2006	Ratio from 0 to 1
		no_data_500_2006	Percentage of No Data land use type within a 500 meter around geocode. This are areas covered by clouds that were not able to classify to a particular land use. Not considered to create LUM. ,2006	Ratio from 0 to 1
		sumarea_500_2006	Sum of different land uses available within buffer area. This is to check wether the land use data covers the buffer area or not. ,2006	Ratio from 0 to 1

		lum_500_2006	Land Use Mix index within a buffer area of 500 meters around geocode. Unitless, from 0 to 1, where 0 represents a single land use in the parcels and 1 represents a perfect balance of all Land Use in the parcels. ,2006	Unitless, from 0 to 1, where 1 indicates mixture of landuses and 0 homogeneity of landuse
		urbanhigh_100_2012	Percentage of high density residential land use type within a 100 meter around geocode. ,2012	Ratio from 0 to 1
		urbanlow_100_2012	Percentage of low density residential land use type within a 100 meter around geocode. ,2012	Ratio from 0 to 1
		com_ind_100_2012	Percentage of commercial and industrial land use type within a 100 meter around geocode. ,2012	Ratio from 0 to 1
		infrast_100_2012	Percentage of infrastructures land use type within a 100 meter around geocode. ,2012	Ratio from 0 to 1
		green_urb_100_2012	Percentage of urban green land use type within a 100 meter around geocode. ,2012	Ratio from 0 to 1
		agric_100_2012	Percentage of agricultural land use type within a 100 meter around geocode. ,2012	Ratio from 0 to 1
		natural_100_2012	Percentage of natural land use type within a 100 meter around geocode. ,2012	Ratio from 0 to 1
		water_100_2012	Percentage of water land use type within a 100 meter around geocode. ,2012	Ratio from 0 to 1
		other_100_2012	Percentage of other land use type within a 100 meter around geocode. ,2012	Ratio from 0 to 1

		no_data_100_2012	Percentage of No Data land use type within a 100 meter around geocode. This are areas covered by clouds that were not able to classify to a particular land use. Not considered to create LUM. ,2012	Ratio from 0 to 1
		sumarea_100_2012	Sum of different land uses available within buffer area. This is to check wether the land use data covers the buffer area or not. ,2012	Ratio from 0 to 1
		in_ua_2012	The geocode is within the Urban Atlas layer (1 = yes, 0 = no). ,2012	Boolean (1 = yes, 0 = no)
		lum_100_2012	Land Use Mix index within a buffer area of 100 meters around geocode. Unitless, from 0 to 1, where 0 represents a single land use in the parcels and 1 represents a perfect balance of all Land Use in the parcels. ,2012	Unitless, from 0 to 1, where 1 indicates mixture of landuses and 0 homogeneity of landuse
		urbanhigh_300_2012	Percentage of high density residential land use type within a 300 meter around geocode. ,2012	Ratio from 0 to 1
		urbanlow_300_2012	Percentage of low density residential land use type within a 300 meter around geocode. ,2012	Ratio from 0 to 1
		com_ind_300_2012	Percentage of commercial and industrial land use type within a 300 meter around geocode. ,2012	Ratio from 0 to 1
		infrast_300_2012	Percentage of infrastructures land use type within a 300 meter around geocode. ,2012	Ratio from 0 to 1
		green_urb_300_2012	Percentage of urban green land use type within a 300 meter around geocode. ,2012	Ratio from 0 to 1
		agric_300_2012	Percentage of agricultural land use type within a 300 meter around geocode. ,2012	Ratio from 0 to 1

		natural_300_2012	Percentage of natural land use type within a 300 meter around geocode. ,2012	Ratio from 0 to 1
		water_300_2012	Percentage of water land use type within a 300 meter around geocode. ,2012	Ratio from 0 to 1
		other_300_2012	Percentage of other land use type within a 300 meter around geocode. ,2012	Ratio from 0 to 1
		no_data_300_2012	Percentage of No Data land use type within a 300 meter around geocode. This are areas covered by clouds that were not able to classify to a particular land use. Not considered to create LUM. ,2012	Ratio from 0 to 1
		sumarea_300_2012	Sum of different land uses available within buffer area. This is to check wether the land use data covers the buffer area or not. ,2012	Ratio from 0 to 1
		lum_300_2012	Land Use Mix index within a buffer area of 300 meters around geocode. Unitless, from 0 to 1, where 0 represents a single land use in the parcels and 1 represents a perfect balance of all Land Use in the parcels. ,2012	Unitless, from 0 to 1, where 1 indicates mixture of landuses and 0 homogeneity of landuse
		urbanhigh_500_2012	Percentage of high density residential land use type within a 500 meter around geocode. ,2012	Ratio from 0 to 1
		urbanlow_500_2012	Percentage of low density residential land use type within a 500 meter around geocode. ,2012	Ratio from 0 to 1
		com_ind_500_2012	Percentage of commercial and industrial land use type within a 500 meter around geocode. ,2012	Ratio from 0 to 1
		infrast_500_2012	Percentage of infrastructures land use type within a 500 meter around geocode. ,2012	Ratio from 0 to 1

		green_urb_500_2012	Percentage of urban green land use type within a 500 meter around geocode. ,2012	Ratio from 0 to 1
		agric_500_2012	Percentage of agricultural land use type within a 500 meter around geocode. ,2012	Ratio from 0 to 1
		natural_500_2012	Percentage of natural land use type within a 500 meter around geocode. ,2012	Ratio from 0 to 1
		water_500_2012	Percentage of water land use type within a 500 meter around geocode. ,2012	Ratio from 0 to 1
		other_500_2012	Percentage of other land use type within a 500 meter around geocode. ,2012	Ratio from 0 to 1
		no_data_500_2012	Percentage of No Data land use type within a 500 meter around geocode. This are areas covered by clouds that were not able to classify to a particular land use. ,2012	Ratio from 0 to 1
		sumarea_500_2012	Sum of different land uses available within buffer area. This is to check wether the land use data covers the buffer area or not. ,2012	Ratio from 0 to 1
		lum_500_2012	Land Use Mix index within a buffer area of 500 meters around geocode. Unitless, from 0 to 1, where 0 represents a single land use in the parcels and 1 represents a perfect balance of all Land Use in the parcels. ,2012	Unitless, from 0 to 1, where 1 indicates mixture of landuses and 0 homogeneity of landuse
		urbanhigh_100_2018	Percentage of high density residential land use type within a 100 meter around geocode. ,2018	Ratio from 0 to 1
		urbanlow_100_2018	Percentage of low density residential land use type within a 100 meter around geocode. ,2018	Ratio from 0 to 1

		com_ind_100_2018	Percentage of commercial and industrial land use type within a 100 meter around geocode. ,2018	Ratio from 0 to 1
		infrast_100_2018	Percentage of infrastructures land use type within a 100 meter around geocode. ,2018	Ratio from 0 to 1
		green_urb_100_2018	Percentage of urban green land use type within a 100 meter around geocode. ,2018	Ratio from 0 to 1
		agric_100_2018	Percentage of agricultural land use type within a 100 meter around geocode. ,2018	Ratio from 0 to 1
		natural_100_2018	Percentage of natural land use type within a 100 meter around geocode. ,2018	Ratio from 0 to 1
		water_100_2018	Percentage of water land use type within a 100 meter around geocode. ,2018	Ratio from 0 to 1
		other_100_2018	Percentage of other land use type within a 100 meter around geocode. ,2018	Ratio from 0 to 1
		no_data_100_2018	Percentage of No Data land use type within a 100 meter around geocode. This are areas covered by clouds that were not able to classify to a particular land use. Not considered to create LUM ,2018	Ratio from 0 to 1
		sumarea_100_2018	Sum of different land uses available within buffer area. This is to check wether the land use data covers the buffer area or not. ,2018	Ratio from 0 to 1
		in_ua_2018	The geocode is within the Urban Atlas layer (1 = yes, 0 = no). ,2018	Boolean (1 = yes, 0 = no)

		lum_100_2018	Land Use Mix index within a buffer area of 100 meters around geocode. Unitless, from 0 to 1, where 0 represents a single land use in the parcels and 1 represents a perfect balance of all Land Use in the parcels. ,2018	Unitless, from 0 to 1, where 1 indicates mixture of landuses and 0 homogeneity of landuse
		urbanhigh_300_2018	Percentage of high density residential land use type within a 300 meter around geocode. ,2018	Ratio from 0 to 1
		urbanlow_300_2018	Percentage of low density residential land use type within a 300 meter around geocode. ,2018	Ratio from 0 to 1
		com_ind_300_2018	Percentage of commercial and industrial land use type within a 300 meter around geocode. ,2018	Ratio from 0 to 1
		infrast_300_2018	Percentage of infrastructures land use type within a 300 meter around geocode. ,2018	Ratio from 0 to 1
		green_urb_300_2018	Percentage of urban green land use type within a 300 meter around geocode. ,2018	Ratio from 0 to 1
		agric_300_2018	Percentage of agricultural land use type within a 300 meter around geocode. ,2018	Ratio from 0 to 1
		natural_300_2018	Percentage of natural land use type within a 300 meter around geocode. ,2018	Ratio from 0 to 1
		water_300_2018	Percentage of water land use type within a 300 meter around geocode. ,2018	Ratio from 0 to 1
		other_300_2018	Percentage of other land use type within a 300 meter around geocode. ,2018	Ratio from 0 to 1

		no_data_300_2018	Percentage of No Data land use type within a 300 meter around geocode. This are areas covered by clouds that were not able to classify to a particular land use. Not considered to create LUM ,2018	Ratio from 0 to 1
		sumarea_300_2018	Sum of different land uses available within buffer area. This is to check wether the land use data covers the buffer area or not. ,2018	Ratio from 0 to 1
		lum_300_2018	Land Use Mix index within a buffer area of 300 meters around geocode. Unitless, from 0 to 1, where 0 represents a single land use in the parcels and 1 represents a perfect balance of all Land Use in the parcels. ,2018	Unitless, from 0 to 1, where 1 indicates mixture of landuses and 0 homogeneity of landuse
		urbanhigh_500_2018	Percentage of high density residential land use type within a 500 meter around geocode. ,2018	Ratio from 0 to 1
		urbanlow_500_2018	Percentage of low density residential land use type within a 500 meter around geocode. ,2018	Ratio from 0 to 1
		com_ind_500_2018	Percentage of commercial and industrial land use type within a 500 meter around geocode. ,2018	Ratio from 0 to 1
		infrast_500_2018	Percentage of infrastructures land use type within a 500 meter around geocode. ,2018	Ratio from 0 to 1
		green_urb_500_2018	Percentage of urban green land use type within a 500 meter around geocode. ,2018	Ratio from 0 to 1
		agric_500_2018	Percentage of agricultural land use type within a 500 meter around geocode. ,2018	Ratio from 0 to 1
		natural_500_2018	Percentage of natural land use type within a 500 meter around geocode. ,2018	Ratio from 0 to 1

		water_500_2018	Percentage of water land use type within a 500 meter around geocode. ,2018	Ratio from 0 to 1
		other_500_2018	Percentage of other land use type within a 500 meter around geocode. ,2018	Ratio from 0 to 1
		no_data_500_2018	Percentage of No Data land use type within a 500 meter around geocode. This are areas covered by clouds that were not able to classify to a particular land use. Not considered to create LUM ,2018	Ratio from 0 to 1
		sumarea_500_2018	Sum of different land uses available within buffer area. This is to check wether the land use data covers the buffer area or not. ,2018	Ratio from 0 to 1
		lum_500_2018	Land Use Mix index within a buffer area of 500 meters around geocode. Unitless, from 0 to 1, where 0 represents a single land use in the parcels and 1 represents a perfect balance of all Land Use in the parcels. ,2018	Unitless, from 0 to 1, where 1 indicates mixture of landuses and 0 homogeneity of landuse
Population		pop_WP_100_2000	Population count within a 100 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2000	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_100_2001	Population count within a 100 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2001	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_100_2002	Population count within a 100 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2002	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_100_2003	Population count within a 100 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2003	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_100_2004	Population count within a 100 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2004	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_100_2005	Population count within a 100 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2005	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_100_2006	Population count within a 100 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2006	Inhabitants

		pop_WP_100_2007	Population count within a 100 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2007	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_100_2008	Population count within a 100 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2008	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_100_2009	Population count within a 100 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2009	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_100_2010	Population count within a 100 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2010	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_100_2011	Population count within a 100 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2011	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_100_2012	Population count within a 100 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2012	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_100_2013	Population count within a 100 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2013	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_100_2014	Population count within a 100 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2014	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_100_2015	Population count within a 100 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2015	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_100_2016	Population count within a 100 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2016	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_100_2017	Population count within a 100 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2017	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_100_2018	Population count within a 100 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2018	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_100_2019	Population count within a 100 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2019	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_100_2020	Population count within a 100 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2020	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_300_2000	Population count within a 300 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2000	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_300_2001	Population count within a 300 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2001	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_300_2002	Population count within a 300 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2002	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_300_2003	Population count within a 300 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2003	Inhabitants

		pop_WP_300_2004	Population count within a 300 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2004	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_300_2005	Population count within a 300 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2005	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_300_2006	Population count within a 300 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2006	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_300_2007	Population count within a 300 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2007	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_300_2008	Population count within a 300 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2008	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_300_2009	Population count within a 300 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2009	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_300_2010	Population count within a 300 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2010	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_300_2011	Population count within a 300 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2011	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_300_2012	Population count within a 300 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2012	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_300_2013	Population count within a 300 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2013	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_300_2014	Population count within a 300 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2014	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_300_2015	Population count within a 300 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2015	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_300_2016	Population count within a 300 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2016	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_300_2017	Population count within a 300 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2017	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_300_2018	Population count within a 300 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2018	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_300_2019	Population count within a 300 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2019	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_300_2020	Population count within a 300 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2020	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_500_2000	Population count within a 500 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2000	Inhabitants

		pop_WP_500_2001	Population count within a 500 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2001	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_500_2002	Population count within a 500 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2002	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_500_2003	Population count within a 500 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2003	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_500_2004	Population count within a 500 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2004	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_500_2005	Population count within a 500 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2005	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_500_2006	Population count within a 500 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2006	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_500_2007	Population count within a 500 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2007	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_500_2008	Population count within a 500 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2008	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_500_2009	Population count within a 500 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2009	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_500_2010	Population count within a 500 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2010	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_500_2011	Population count within a 500 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2011	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_500_2012	Population count within a 500 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2012	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_500_2013	Population count within a 500 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2013	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_500_2014	Population count within a 500 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2014	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_500_2015	Population count within a 500 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2015	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_500_2016	Population count within a 500 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2016	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_500_2017	Population count within a 500 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2017	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_500_2018	Population count within a 500 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2018	Inhabitants

		pop_WP_500_2019	Population count within a 500 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2019	Inhabitants
		pop_WP_500_2020	Population count within a 500 meter buffer around geocode. Using WP. ,2020	Inhabitants
		pop_GHS_100_1990	Population count within a 100 meter buffer around geocode. Using GHS. ,1990	Inhabitants
		pop_GHS_100_2000	Population count within a 100 meter buffer around geocode. Using GHS. ,2000	Inhabitants
		pop_GHS_100_2015	Population count within a 100 meter buffer around geocode. Using GHS. ,2015	Inhabitants
		pop_GHS_300_1990	Population count within a 300 meter buffer around geocode. Using GHS. ,1990	Inhabitants
		pop_GHS_300_2000	Population count within a 300 meter buffer around geocode. Using GHS. ,2000	Inhabitants
		pop_GHS_300_2015	Population count within a 300 meter buffer around geocode. Using GHS. ,2015	Inhabitants
		pop_GHS_500_1990	Population count within a 500 meter buffer around geocode. Using GHS. ,1990	Inhabitants
		pop_GHS_500_2000	Population count within a 500 meter buffer around geocode. Using GHS. ,2000	Inhabitants
		pop_GHS_500_2015	Population count within a 500 meter buffer around geocode. Using GHS. ,2015	Inhabitants
Roads		dist_streets_2014	Euclidian distance to the closest road of category 'streets'. ,2014	Meters (m)
		length_streets_2014_b100	Total length of road sections of category 'streets' within a 100m radius buffer. ,2014	Meters (m)
		length_streets_2014_b300	Total length of road sections of category 'streets' within a 300m radius buffer. ,2014	Meters (m)
		length_streets_2014_b500	Total length of road sections of category 'streets' within a 500m radius buffer. ,2014	Meters (m)
		qaGrowth_streets_2014	Relative variation in roads cumulative length over one year. ,2014	Percentage (0 - 100%)

		qaSaturation_streets_2014	Ratio between roads cumulated length at one point in time and the cumulated length expected at saturated level (approximation of "complete" dataset). ,2014	Percentage (0 - 100%)
		dist_roads_2014	Euclidian distance to the closest road of category 'roads'. ,2014	Meters (m)
		length_roads_2014_b100	Total length of road sections of category 'roads' within a 100m radius buffer. ,2014	Meters (m)
		length_roads_2014_b300	Total length of road sections of category 'roads' within a 300m radius buffer. ,2014	Meters (m)
		length_roads_2014_b500	Total length of road sections of category 'roads' within a 500m radius buffer. ,2014	Meters (m)
		qaGrowth_roads_2014	Relative variation in roads cumulative length over one year. ,2014	Percentage (0 - 100%)
		qaSaturation_roads_2014	Ratio between roads cumulated length at one point in time and the cumulated length expected at saturated level (approximation of "complete" dataset). ,2014	Percentage (0 - 100%)
		dist_major_roads_2014	Euclidian distance to the closest road of category 'major_roads'. ,2014	Meters (m)
		length_major_roads_2014_b100	Total length of road sections of category 'major_roads' within a 100m radius buffer. ,2014	Meters (m)
		length_major_roads_2014_b300	Total length of road sections of category 'major_roads' within a 300m radius buffer. ,2014	Meters (m)
		length_major_roads_2014_b500	Total length of road sections of category 'major_roads' within a 500m radius buffer. ,2014	Meters (m)
		qaGrowth_major_roads_2014	Relative variation in roads cumulative length over one year. ,2014	Percentage (0 - 100%)

		qaSaturation_major_roads_2014	Ratio between roads cumulated length at one point in time and the cumulated length expected at saturated level (approximation of "complete" dataset). ,2014	Percentage (0 - 100%)
		dist_any_road_2014	Euclidian distance to the closest road of category 'any_road'. ,2014	Meters (m)
		dist_streets_2018	Euclidian distance to the closest road of category 'streets'. ,2018	Meters (m)
		length_streets_2018_b100	Total length of road sections of category 'streets' within a 100m radius buffer. ,2018	Meters (m)
		length_streets_2018_b300	Total length of road sections of category 'streets' within a 300m radius buffer. ,2018	Meters (m)
		length_streets_2018_b500	Total length of road sections of category 'streets' within a 500m radius buffer. ,2018	Meters (m)
		qaGrowth_streets_2018	Relative variation in roads cumulative length over one year. ,2018	Percentage (0 - 100%)
		qaSaturation_streets_2018	Ratio between roads cumulated length at one point in time and the cumulated length expected at saturated level (approximation of "complete" dataset). ,2018	Percentage (0 - 100%)
		dist_roads_2018	Euclidian distance to the closest road of category 'roads'. ,2018	Meters (m)
		length_roads_2018_b100	Total length of road sections of category 'roads' within a 100m radius buffer. ,2018	Meters (m)
		length_roads_2018_b300	Total length of road sections of category 'roads' within a 300m radius buffer. ,2018	Meters (m)
		length_roads_2018_b500	Total length of road sections of category 'roads' within a 500m radius buffer. ,2018	Meters (m)
		qaGrowth_roads_2018	Relative variation in roads cumulative length over one year. ,2018	Percentage (0 - 100%)

		qaSaturation_roads_2018	Ratio between roads cumulated length at one point in time and the cumulated length expected at saturated level (approximation of "complete" dataset). ,2018	Percentage (0 - 100%)
		dist_major_roads_2018	Euclidian distance to the closest road of category 'major_roads'. ,2018	Meters (m)
		length_major_roads_2018_b100	Total length of road sections of category 'major_roads' within a 100m radius buffer. ,2018	Meters (m)
		length_major_roads_2018_b300	Total length of road sections of category 'major_roads' within a 300m radius buffer. ,2018	Meters (m)
		length_major_roads_2018_b500	Total length of road sections of category 'major_roads' within a 500m radius buffer. ,2018	Meters (m)
		qaGrowth_major_roads_2018	Relative variation in roads cumulative length over one year. ,2018	Percentage (0 - 100%)
		qaSaturation_major_roads_2018	Ratio between roads cumulated length at one point in time and the cumulated length expected at saturated level (approximation of "complete" dataset). ,2018	Percentage (0 - 100%)
		dist_any_road_2018	Euclidian distance to the closest road of category 'any_road'. ,2018	Meters (m)
		hull	Distance to the hull limit. Any "dist" indicator for which the value is higher than this value (ie. for which the closest road is further than the hull), there is a possibility that a closer road of this category exists outside the hull than the one identified, but it is not closer than the distance to the hull limit (>10km). ,Any	Meters (m)
SOCIAL ENRICHMENT *				
Social interactions	Household structure	enr_Hhstructure_t	Household composition (e.g. proportion of families, same-sex and heterosexual marriages and couples, single parent families)	

Socioeconomic circumstances and Sociodemographic characteristics	Population density	enr_Popdens_t	Residents per km2	
	Age structure	enr_agestructure_t	Proportions by status (e.g. preschool children, schoolchildren, young adults, adults, pensioners) Proportions by age groups	
	Old-age ratio	enr_Oldageratio_t	Proportions of population below age of retirement (e.g. < 65 years) (national standards concerning the retirement/working age must be considered)	
	Youth ratio	enr_Youthratio_t	Proportions of population below adulthood (e.g. 18 years) (national standards of 'start of adulthood' must be considered)	
	Net migration rate	enr_Netmigrat_t	Difference between the number of people entering (migration) a region and people leaving (emigration) a region	
	Level of education	enr_Edulevel_t	International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED) (http://uis.unesco.org/en/topic/international-standard-classification-education-isced)	
	Income categories	enr_Incomecat_t	Proportions of households in certain income categories (national standards on income distribution must be considered)	
	Unemployment rates	enr_uerate_t	Proportions in total and if possible for different age groups (e.g.: 25-54;55-65) (national standards concerning the retirement/working age must be reported)	
	Youth unemployment rates	enr_ueyouthrate_t	Proportions of unemployed in e.g. 15 to 24- year olds	
	Unemployment rates in men & women	enr_uesexrate_t	Proportions of unemployed men and women	

Systems, institutions and priorities of the political economy	Child poverty	enr_Childpov_t	Proportion of children at poverty risk (national standards on e.g. income distribution, breadline etc. must be considered)	
	Old-age poverty	enr_oldagepov_t	Proportion of elderly persons at poverty risk (national standards on e.g. income distribution, breadline etc. must be considered)	
	Deprivation Score	enr_Deprivscore_t	Indicators of deprivation and poverty (e.g. welfare receivers, Townsend deprivation score: unemployment, persons per room, non-car ownership, non-home ownership) (national standards on income distribution must be considered)	
	Voter participation	enr_Voterparticip_t	Proportions of voter participation in national and regional elections (national standards of elections system must be considered)	
	Per capita crime rates	enr_crimeratepc_t	Crime rates, possibly distinguishing between types of crime	
Sociodemographic characteristics with high impact on Social norms, Cultural values	Migration background	enr_Migbackgr_t	Proportions of residents with migration background	
	Foreign citizenship	enr_Foreigcitizen_t	Proportions of residents with a foreign citizenship	
	First language	enr_firstlan_t	Proportions of households with first language deviating from official language(s) 19	
	Religious affiliation	enr_Religiousaff_t	Proportions of religious denominations (e.g. Buddhists, Catholics)	
<i>* The variable names for the social exposome indicators (from Milestone 16) were suggested by WP7.</i>				

